
TRANSLANGUAGING PRACTICES IN ORAL LANGUAGE CONTEXT: DESIGNING MULTILINGUAL INSTRUCTIONAL TASKS FOR EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate how students engage and practice translanguaging during oral communication and to develop multilingual instructional tasks informed by these practices. Second-year undergraduate education students represent the respondents. Using a mixed-methods approach with a convergent parallel design, the study employs a survey to explore students' perceptions of translanguaging in group presentations and discussions, along with its effects on their educational experiences. Discourse analysis of audio recordings and transcriptions examines students' translanguaging activities. Findings reveal that students consistently practice translanguaging to enhance comprehension and communication, with the intra-sentential type being the most prevalent. The study highlights the need to encourage congruent lexicalization and increase the use of translation and humor for various functions. Proposed multilingual instructional tasks include group activities utilizing multiple languages, peer translation exercises, role-playing scenarios, and oral presentations encouraging translanguaging. These tasks aim to foster inclusivity, motivation, and engagement while supporting communication, comprehension, and participation.

INTRODUCTION

In this interconnected world, the English language functions as the Lingua Franca across various sectors like Science, Technology, Business, Commerce, and even in Education. Learning English is one of the prerequisites for achieving academic, professional, and personal goals in school. This makes proficiency in English an asset and essential for seizing opportunities. It reveals how significant English is for the competence and proficiency of all students, making them better prepared in this globalized world. This leads to the development of policies enforced by educational institutions to use English as one of the primary mediums of instruction.

However, it is important to recognize that the Philippines boasts a rich tapestry of cultural and linguistic diversity with 180 languages and counting (Lewis et al., 2013). Filipinos

encounter numerous languages within communities, making them bilingual/multilingual. In a bilingual or multilingual classroom setting, the selection of language by instructors holds considerable significance in facilitating students' comprehension. However, challenges arise due to the implementation of English as a primary medium of instruction. Many students use their first language in oral contexts because they are not proficient enough in English.

This led to the employment of multilingual or bilingual strategies. When students enter the classroom, they bring with them a diverse linguistic repertoire, including their native tongues, which they strategically use in learning additional languages (Carroll & Morales, 2016). This approach is termed "translanguaging," wherein multiple languages are employed for pedagogical purposes (Vogel and Garcia, 2017). Since then, it has developed into a complex concept that encompasses the dynamic and fluid use of linguistic resources for learning, communication, and meaning-making. It fosters cooperation and facilitates a greater understanding of the subject matter (García & Wei, 2014).

Translanguaging, which was previously associated with code-switching, has evolved (Garcia, 2009). Code-switching was seen negatively as a consequence of native language interference in second-language acquisition (Creese & Blackledge, 2010). In contrast, translanguaging is recognized as an effective approach that utilizes many languages to improve comprehension and communication (Lewis et al., 2012). Translanguaging in EFL environments has been proven to increase student involvement, engagement, motivation, and self-confidence (Lewis et al., 2012). In an ESL context, translanguaging is one of the approaches that prevents marginalizing language learners who experience demotivation and exclusion.

METHODS

Research Design

The research employed a mixed-method design, specifically, a convergent parallel design was followed, where both types of data were collected in the same period or phase but analyzed separately. The results are then combined to determine whether the findings confirm or disconfirm each other (Creswell, 2013). The quantitative phase aimed to explain translanguaging practices through numerical data and statistical analysis. The qualitative phase used discourse analysis to further interpret the quantitative results by studying language in context, specifically analyzing the translanguaging practices of the participants. By combining both approaches, the researchers were able to confirm and supplement findings, offering a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the research issue.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

The locale of the study is at Isabela State University, which is the locale of the study since choosing this would be convenient, making the location ideal for the researchers. In addition, the College of Education was one of the departments that provided its students great exposure to so much speaking, which will help the researchers to have sufficient data that represents the research participants' translanguaging practices.

The participants of this study are sophomore students at the College of Education of Isabela State University-Echague. The research participants include programs from Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd), Bachelor of Early Childhood Education (BECEd), Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd), Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd), and Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education. The researchers used the formula by Cochran (1997) to determine the sample size with a 95% confidence level and a margin of error of 5%. Moreover, the researcher chose the education students since they are also exposed to oral presentations or discussions. The Sophomores are also chosen since in their classroom setting, they use several languages based on their subject to express themselves or in an oral language context.

Research Instrument

This study employed a mixed-method approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. For the quantitative component, a 20-item Likert scale questionnaire was used to assess participants' perceptions of translanguageing practices during presentations and discussions. Participants were asked to rate their agreement with each statement on a scale from 1 to 4. To ensure the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach's Alpha analysis was conducted, yielding a score of 0.715898, which is above the acceptable threshold of 0.7 (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Content validity was also considered to ensure the relevance of the questions. In the qualitative component, discourse analysis was employed through audio recordings and transcriptions to explore the students' actual translanguageing practices during group discussions. Teachers coordinated the speaking tasks to ensure they aligned with the educational objectives. This approach allowed for an in-depth examination of the participants' language use, focusing on creative and critical thinking. It provided insights into how students navigated conversations, negotiated meanings, and positioned themselves, enhancing the understanding of group dynamics and translanguageing in oral communication.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

This data collection approach aimed to investigate the translanguageing strategies utilized during spoken language activities by incoming sophomore Education students at Isabela State University - Echague Campus. The researchers first wrote an authorization letter to the dean of the department to seek permission for the study. After receiving approval, the total population of incoming second-year Education learners for the Academic Year 2024-2025 was identified. A Cochran formula was used to determine the sample size of participants. Availability Sampling was then applied for convenience, selecting students who were present in the class. Data was collected personally by the researchers, who also sought permission from the subject teacher and the students regarding the use of audio recording and classroom observation during group presentations. Prior to data collection, the researchers explained the study to the class and assured the respondents that the data would remain anonymous and confidential. Audio recordings were strictly for the study's purpose and would protect participants' privacy.

The researchers distributed a 20-item, 4-point Likert scale survey to second-year students from various programs (BSE, BEED, BECED, BTLED, and BPEd). After the survey, selected students from each program participated in a group presentation, which served as the elicitation procedure for discourse analysis through audio recording and transcription. The researchers coordinated with the teacher regarding the presentation activity, which was

designed to elicit translanguaging behaviors. Each group's presentation was monitored by a researcher, and audio recordings were made, with each recording lasting up to 15 minutes. The recording began when the students started speaking.

For data management, all collected information was securely stored in an encrypted digital repository, with access limited to authorized study team members. A summary of the results was sent to the participating students. At the end of the semester, the data collection technique was reviewed, and recommendations for improving future data collection efforts were made.

This study uses both quantitative and qualitative data analysis to examine the translanguaging practices of sophomore education students. Descriptive statistics were applied to analyze the questionnaire data, summarizing responses, calculating means, and identifying common trends in perceptions of translanguaging during presentations and discussions. For the qualitative data, oral language recordings from group presentations were transcribed and analyzed using Braun and Clarke's six-phase thematic analysis. This approach provides a comprehensive understanding of how translanguaging is used in the oral language context among participants at Isabela State University - Echague.

Ethical Considerations

For ethical considerations, the researchers assured the respondents of the study that the data that is collected will remain anonymous and confidential, and audio recording is only used for the sake of the study, protecting their privacy and the information they share for the success of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Translanguaging Practices of the Research Participants in their Oral Language Presentation

Table 1 shows the effectiveness of translanguaging practices across key dimensions: comprehension, communication, motivation, and inclusivity, with a grand mean score of 3.55, indicating that the students always practice translanguaging.

Table 4 shows the five translanguaging practices observed in 1,092 sentences during discussions and presentations, highlighting their frequency and percentage. The most common practice is intra-sentential translanguaging (53.20%), in which speakers move between languages within a sentence to accommodate preferences and clarify concepts. Canagarajah (2011) identifies translanguaging, the most common and highest-occurring practice in multilingual environments, as a natural way for students to switch between languages to clarify concepts and adapt to peers' linguistic preferences. Following this are insertion translanguaging (9.89%), which incorporates single words or terms from another language to improve clarity, and total translanguaging (31.02%), wherein speakers completely transition to another language for better explanation. Inter-sentential translanguaging, which involves language switching between sentences, is less prevalent (7.49%). Congruent lexicalization (0%), blending closely related languages within grammatical structures, was not observed, aligning with Putrawan's (2022) findings that this approach is avoided due to its potential to confuse learners.

Table 1. Translanguaging Practices of the Respondents in their Oral Presentations

Translanguaging Practices	Mean	Qualitative Description
Comprehension and Translanguaging		
1. Using translanguaging during presentations and discussions helps me better understand the subject matter.	3.74	Always
2. I feel that practicing translanguaging enables me to effectively utilize my entire linguistic repertoire during presentations and discussions.	3.5	Always
3. Translanguaging during presentations and discussions enhances my ability to communicate complex ideas more clearly.	3.65	Always
4. I believe that translanguaging fosters deeper comprehension of the subject matter among my classmates during presentations and discussions.	3.5	Always
5. Engaging in translanguaging during presentations and discussions empowers me to harness my full range of linguistic resources for improved learning outcomes	3.46	Always
Weighted Mean	3.57	Always
Translanguaging and Inclusivity and Diversity		
6. I believe that using translanguaging in the classroom values students' diverse linguistic backgrounds.	3.53	Always
7. Translanguaging practices create a more inclusive learning environment for all students.	3.6	Always
8. Translanguaging enables students to capitalize on their complete linguistic repertoire in the learning process.	3.4	Always
9. Implementing translanguaging strategies promotes a sense of belonging among students from different linguistic backgrounds.	3.55	Always
10. Translanguaging fosters a greater appreciation for linguistic diversity in the classroom	3.51	Always
Weighted Mean	3.52	Always
Translanguaging and Communication		
11. When I use translanguaging during presentations and discussions, I notice improved communication among my classmates.	3.61	Always
12. I find it easier to collaborate with my peers when we practice translanguaging during presentations and discussions.	3.63	Always
13. I feel that practicing translanguaging in presentations and discussions contributes to a more supportive learning environment.	3.58	Always

14. In my experience, using a translanguaging strategies during classroom presentations and discussions lead to increased peer support.	3.52	Always
15. When we utilize translanguaging in presentations and discussions, it fosters a more cooperative and engaged learning atmosphere.	3.52	Always
Weighted Mean	3.57	Always

Translanguaging and Motivation

16. When I use translanguaging during presentations and discussions, I feel more engaged in the learning process.	3.44	Always
17. Practicing translanguaging in presentations and discussions increases my motivation to learn and participate.	3.59	Always
18. I believe that using translanguaging strategies during classroom presentations and discussions boosts my self-confidence	3.60	Always
19. When we engage in translanguaging during presentations and discussions, I notice that my classmates are more engaged and motivated.	3.5	Always
20. In my experience, translanguaging in classroom presentations and discussions fosters a greater sense of self-confidence among my peers.	3.60	Always
Weighted Mean	3.55	Always

Functions of Translanguaging

Based on Table 2, the analysis of 1,092 instances of translanguaging revealed a dominant focus on task-referring functions, which accounted for the majority of observed occurrences. Elaboration was the most frequent function (59.98%), highlighting its role in providing detailed explanations and expanding ideas. This aligns with García and Li Wei (2014), who emphasize that elaboration leverages multiple linguistic resources to deepen understanding.

Table 2. The Functions of Translanguaging

Functions of Translanguaging	Frequency of Occurrence	Percent
Task-Referring Function		
1. Elaboration	655	59.98
2. Asking Question	184	16.85
3. Giving Examples	143	13.10
4. Interpretation	72	6.60
5. Translation	10	0.92
Non-Task-Referring Functions		
6. Chit-Chat	18	1.65
7. Requesting	7	0.64
8. Humor	3	0.27

On the other hand, asking questions (16.85%) emerged as another significant function, promoting clarification and active participation in discussions. Giving examples (13.10%) was also notable, helping to reinforce understanding through relatable scenarios. Less frequent task-referring functions included interpretation (6.60%) and translation (0.92%), which served to bridge comprehension gaps, particularly for participants with varying linguistic proficiencies. Non-task-referring functions were rare, comprising only 2.55% of the total instances. Among these, chit-chat (1.65%) was the most common, fostering informal rapport, while requesting (0.64%) and humor (0.27%) were observed infrequently, reflecting their limited role in structured educational settings. Cenoz and Gorter (2011) stated that non-task-referring functions are less emphasized in formal learning environments, where cognitive and communicative objectives are the focus.

I. Translanguaging Practices of the Research Participants in their Oral Language Presentation

Translanguaging and Comprehension

Translanguaging enhances comprehension by bridging vocabulary gaps and simplifying complex concepts, allowing students to move between languages to better express and understand ideas. It fosters clearer communication and more inclusive discussions, as highlighted by Creese and Blackledge (2010). The practice is especially effective in helping students articulate complex concepts during presentations, improving their overall understanding, as shown by studies like Baker (2001) and Sayer (2013). Even in less obvious instances, translanguaging still aids comprehension by empowering students and promoting meaningful engagement, as noted by Wei (2018). However, if a student has limited competency in the languages being used, language switching may be mentally demanding for them and hinder their ability to understand, according to MacSwan (2017).

Translanguaging and Communication

Translanguaging and communication were frequently used by students to enhance communication and understanding in the classroom. Using multiple languages allows students to express ideas clearly, understand different perspectives, and resolve misunderstandings, fostering more confident and inclusive discussions. An indicator that was frequently used by students highlights how translanguaging improves collaboration and creates a supportive peer environment, as confirmed in a study by Cenoz and Gorter (2021). However, the less frequent indicator shows that some students view formal communication as requiring a single language, often English, which may limit translanguaging. Challenges such as inconsistent teaching strategies and language anxiety, noted by Hornberger and Link (2012) and Macaro (2018), may also hinder its application.

Translanguaging and Motivation

Translanguaging plays a significant role in fostering motivation, engagement, and self-confidence among students in multilingual classrooms. It serves as a tool to encourage participation and create an inclusive environment where students feel free to express themselves. Research underscores its positive impact, demonstrating how translanguaging enhances student motivation and fosters a sense of community (García & Wei, 2014). Boosting self-confidence emerges as a key benefit of translanguaging, empowering students and promoting greater peer involvement and collaboration. Studies reveal that using multiple languages in group activities deepens cooperation, improves communication skills, and strengthens social bonds (Otheguy et al., 2015; García & Wei, 2014). Despite its advantages,

challenges such as lower levels of personal engagement in certain contexts highlight the need for culturally sensitive teaching strategies to ensure inclusivity. Research emphasizes the importance of valuing diverse student experiences (Huang, 2018). Nevertheless, translanguaging remains an effective strategy for fostering motivation, collaboration, and meaningful interactions in diverse educational settings.

Translanguaging and Inclusivity, and Diversity

By allowing students to interact more deeply with the content and creating a feeling of belonging, translanguaging is essential to advancing inclusivity and linguistic diversity in the classroom. Students especially value how translanguaging fosters a welcoming, cooperative atmosphere that overcomes linguistic and cultural barriers to improve cooperation and communication. This approach also validates students' linguistic identities, boosting their confidence and academic involvement, which enhances their connection to the material and peers (García & Kleyn, 2022; González, 2009). However, challenges occur when traditional academic institutions limit translanguaging's full application, which can reduce its effectiveness. Students nevertheless see the benefits of translanguaging in improving creativity, comprehension, and engagement in spite of these limitations (Creese & Blackledge, 2010; Wei, 2018).

Types of Translanguaging

Intra-sentential

Intra-sentential translanguaging involves switching between languages within a sentence or clause. As supported by Novianti's (2003) findings, this practice helps participants express their thoughts seamlessly without searching for correct words or terms in one language. For instance, a student participant shared, "*And pansin niyo rin na maraming families ang nagreklamo sa new curriculum natin kasi ngayong generation natin is ang daming nakakakuha ng with high honors and with honors.*" (You might also notice that many families are complaining about our new curriculum because there are a lot of students receiving high honors and honors.) This demonstrates how intra-sentential translanguaging supports smooth, clear, and effective communication by enabling speakers to borrow terms from another language and convey nuanced ideas without interruption.

Entire

Entire translanguaging occurs when students use their preferred language fully, helping them express ideas clearly and deeply. It fosters natural communication, understanding, and inclusivity by allowing students to use all their language skills. For example, one student confidently delivered a complete thought in English during a group discussion—"We think that the main reason for that problem is lack of support (?) from knowledgeable people....". This approach, supported by peers, helped students clarify ideas, collaborate effectively, and engage in meaningful discussions. It aligns with García's (2014) view that translanguaging blends languages to improve understanding and Martin's (2017) findings that it promotes inclusivity and teamwork in learning.

Insertion

It is the third most common practice during group discussions and presentations and involves incorporating single words or short phrases from one language into sentences primarily structured in another. For instance, a student participant stated, "*Kase diba minsan din kahit gusto mag-aral ng mga studyante pero dahil sa kakulangan ng learning materials eh*

wala na hanggang doon nalang" ("Because sometimes, even if students want to study, due to the lack of learning materials, they can only go so far"). While this approach facilitates communication, it is less dynamic, as noted by Muysken (2000). Li (2018) adds that insertion translanguaging helps convey cultural nuances and complex ideas effectively.

Inter-sentential

Inter-sentential translanguaging is when a speaker shifts between languages within a sentence or clause to facilitate expression and communication. For example, "*Kailangan nila maging handa*, when it comes to creating materials, *para sa mga estudyante nila*." (They need to be ready, when it comes to creating materials, for their students.) In the following sentence, the student participant starts the phrase in Tagalog and then switches to English for the final portion, then switches again to Tagalog. This practice demonstrates bilingualism and fulfills a particular communication function. This also enables individuals to employ lexicons that might be more accurate or recognizable in one language, as exemplified by the expression "when it comes to," which may lack a direct Tagalog equivalent. For instance, Grosjean (1982) explores how bilinguals often switch languages to convey nuanced meanings or cultural references that may not be fully captured in one language.

Congruent Lexicalization

Congruent lexicalization refers to the mixing of words and grammar from different languages in a sentence, which did not occur in this study, as it was observed 0% of the time. This suggests that participants avoided language mixing to maintain clarity or to meet the formal, structured requirements of the tasks. This aligns with Perez-Llantada's (2021) findings that academic tasks often prioritize clear, structured language over creative mixing.

Translanguaging Functions

Task-Referring Function

Elaboration

Students most frequently practice translanguaging during elaboration, particularly in group discussions and presentations, where they clarify or expand on ideas. One student shared, "*Yung mga tamad magturo, hindi nila na-e-encourage yung students kasi nga tamad sila, tapos mga English pa nila nakaka-antok*." (The lazy teachers, they don't encourage students because they're lazy, and their English is boring to listen to.) This highlights how students use their linguistic repertoire to clarify and ensure understanding when English explanations fall short. Translanguaging helps to bridge gaps in understanding and supports an inclusive environment where all students can engage more fully in learning (Garcia & Wei, 2014).

Asking Questions

Translanguaging also serves as a tool for students to ask questions, helping them deepen their understanding of the material. One student mentioned, "*So bakit kaya ganun? Bakit tayo nasa lowest sixth place among 81 countries?*" (Why is that? Why are we in the lowest sixth place among 81 countries?). This example illustrates how students use both languages to express curiosity and explore complex issues. Translanguaging enables students to ask questions in ways that deepen their engagement with content, thus encouraging more meaningful learning experiences (García, 2009).

Giving Examples

Students use translanguaging to offer examples that make abstract or complex concepts more relatable and understandable. One student stated, *"For example, sa mga isolated areas sa Pilipinas, dahil sa kakulangan sa pera, hindi accessible ang education."* (For example, in the isolated areas in the Philippines, due to a lack of money, education is not accessible.). This shows how translanguaging helps students to provide concrete, real-world examples that facilitate comprehension. Using examples is an effective way to make abstract concepts tangible and accessible for students, improving overall understanding (Cox, 2020).

Interpretation

Translanguaging is also used to interpret and explain ideas with more clarity, drawing on both languages to express nuanced meanings. One student said, *"Kailangan nating pagtutunan ng pansin ang pag-aaral kasi kailangan natin i-enhance yung qualities at skills natin as future teachers."* (We need to focus on studying because we need to enhance our qualities and skills as future teachers.). This demonstrates how students use translanguaging to provide further explanation and ensure that their peers fully understand the message. Translanguaging not only aids comprehension but also supports students in making complex ideas more accessible and relevant (Garcia & Wei, 2014).

Translation

Translation, as a function of translanguaging, is often used by students to bridge language gaps and ensure their messages are understood by everyone. One student shared, *"Teachers should be flexible para po mas maganda nilang maipaliwanag yung content ng lesson nila."* (Teachers should be flexible so they can explain the content of their lessons better.). This highlights how translanguaging helps students navigate between languages to communicate effectively and ensure understanding. Translanguaging is a powerful tool for enhancing communication, making it easier for students to express ideas clearly and inclusively (Garcia & Wei, 2014).

Non-Task-Referring Function

Chit-chat

Chit-chat or informal conversation is a common function of translanguaging, where students casually converse with one another in a mix of languages. One student casually said, *"Eto na yung sakin oh, tigiisa tayong questions na aansweran."* (mine, we'll each answer one question.). This informal use of both languages helps create a relaxed and supportive atmosphere for students, which encourages participation. Such informal interactions lay the foundation for more meaningful engagement in academic settings, helping students become more comfortable in discussions (Wei, 2011).

Requesting

Lastly, students use translanguaging when requesting clarification or further explanation. One student asked, *"Ano yung sinabi mo kanina? Can you explain it again?"* (What did you say earlier? Can you explain it again?). This demonstrates how students use translanguaging to ask for clarification in a manner that ensures full understanding. Translanguaging provides a supportive environment for students to express their needs and seek clarification, promoting more effective learning (De Los Reyes, 2019).

Humor

Humor, though less common, plays a significant role in translinguaging by lightening the mood and fostering peer connections in multilingual settings. For example, a student joked, "Uhhh... mag teacher ka hahahaha." (Uhhh... be a teacher hahaha), blending Filipino and English in a way that resonated with peers and broke the ice. This demonstrates how humor not only enhances peer relationships but also encourages participation and interaction, which are crucial for meaningful engagement in learning environments. By tailoring humor to the group's cultural and linguistic context, it becomes an effective tool for easing tension and promoting a collaborative atmosphere (Wei, 2011; García & Wei, 2014).

II. DESIGN MULTILINGUAL INSTRUCTIONAL TASK

The study identifies two key areas for improvement in translinguaging practices: enhancing motivation (mean score: 3.55) and inclusivity and diversity (mean score: 3.52). Additionally, there is a need to encourage students to use less practiced translinguaging in types and functions, such as congruent lexicalization, translation, and humor. To address these gaps, the study developed a multilingual instructional toolkit titled **The Inclusive Engagement Toolkit: Translinguaging for Diverse Classrooms**. This toolkit provides structured yet flexible activities that promote inclusivity, motivation, and the use of diverse linguistic practices. It includes chapters focusing on fostering belonging and cultural appreciation, boosting motivation and peer engagement through debates and creative exercises, encouraging congruent lexicalization in real-life contexts, and integrating translation and humor to create engaging, inclusive classrooms. The toolkit aims to empower educators to validate students' linguistic identities, bridge language gaps, and foster a collaborative, multilingual learning environment.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The current study aimed to explore the translinguaging practices of Education students in their oral language presentations, focusing on two specific research questions: identifying the translinguaging practices used in their oral presentations, and determining how these findings can inform the design of multilingual instructional tasks. In light of the aforementioned findings, translinguaging practices create a learning space where students can assert their linguistic identities. By the application of translinguaging, students can actively participate in academic activities, discussions, brainstorming, and sharing their ideas on certain topics. Also, this practice enhances comprehension, improves knowledge construction of the students, and by accepting the concept of translinguaging and integrating it into their pedagogy, educators can create a learning environment that not only accommodates students from a variety of linguistic backgrounds but also promotes more effective teaching techniques. As a result, the study contributes to the body of knowledge about translinguaging and its educational applications in higher education. However, it is important to understand that the present study is concentrated on particular samples. Future studies might investigate the long-term effects of translinguaging on students' language development and academic progress, given the current research's restricted scope. This would provide a deeper understanding of the intricacies of translinguaging.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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